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Strengthening the Professional Identity of Primary School Teachers through Effective Time Management

Abstract: The article outlines the professional identity of primary school teachers, which is a component of artistic excellence that involves performance in the career field of professionalization.

Values of the axiological system of professional identity are addressed and emphasis is placed on the examination of social awareness and time management – a factor that contributes to the personal development of teachers, high achievement, personal satisfaction, and fulfilment, implying compliance with methodological principles in the valorisation of time. The concept of time management comprises a number of definitions that describe a system of activities, processes, and resources that we use to make effective use of our time. Time management is a way of living and working, in which we manage our own time efficiently.

Keywords: professional identity, artistic excellence, teachers, primary education, artistic transposition, social resonance, time management.

Rezumat: Articolul prezintă descrierea identității profesionale a cadrelor didactice din învățământul primar, aceasta fiind o componentă a excelenței artistice ce presupune performarea în cariera domeniului de profesionalizare. Textul vizează unele valori ale sistemului axiologic al identității profesionale. Accentul se pune pe examinarea rezonanței sociale și gestionarea corectă a timpului, factor ce contribuie la dezvoltarea personală a cadrelor didactice, la atingerea celor mai înalte scopuri, la satisfacția și împlinirea personală și presupune respectarea principiilor metodologice în valorificarea timpului. Conceptul de gestionare a timpului cuprinde o serie de definiții care descriu un sistem de activități, procese și resurse pe care le folosim pentru a utiliza în mod eficient timpul propriu. Managementul timpului este un mod de viață și de muncă, prin care ne folosim propriul timp într-un mod eficient.

Cuvinte-cheie: identitate profesională, excelență artistică, cadre didactice, învățământ primar, transpunere artistică, rezonanță socială, gestionarea timpului.

Professional identification in primary education has an emotional impact on teachers, signifying a more effective approach to the educational process. The term *identity* encompasses principles, values, knowledge and skills woven into integrity [12, p. 194].

Therefore, professional identity is all about the effective conduct of the teaching process, namely:

- use of the curriculum and the methodological guidelines to implement the modular curriculum;
- the development of long-term projects and related teaching materials;

- active-participatory, learner-centered learning;
- identification of opportunities to make the educational process more efficient;
- constructive communication and networking in the social and teaching environment;
- monitoring one's own learning and training process [8, p. 78].

Figure 1 renders the values of the professional identity of artistic excellence of primary school teachers:

Figure 1. A graphic representation of professional identity

Scientific concerns about *artistic transposition and sense of humor* are gaining momentum in the system of language and literature education objectives, resulting in the development of strategies in this direction. They are aimed at:

- establishing the values of the mother tongue, national literature, universal literature, and the ethnic groups concerned;
- attitudinal, affective integration into national and European value systems;
- the development of personal values;
- training in the ability to receive and produce values;
- education in the spirit of national pride and fundamental civic obligations [7, p. 4].

The examination of *social resonance and time management* is felt differently by each individual. For example, a song may give pleasure to one person and displeasure to another.

The phenomenon of resonance is much more complex when it occurs in the process of social interaction, and its explanation becomes much more elusive. As an example, the following situation may be envisaged: subject A interacts with subject B; both subjects were frustrated in their childhood by the joy of receiving gifts; nowadays, subject A feels great pleasure when he has the opportunity and the possibility to bring joy to his loved ones by giving them gifts, and subject B feels fulfilled and at peace when he receives gifts from family

or friends. In this example, resonance is determined by both similarity and complementarity, with causes on both the conscious and unconscious levels [2].

Time constitutes a very valuable resource in educational context. Its limited, irreversible, irrevocable, non-transferable nature gives it uniqueness and value. Time, in turn, gives value to activity, i.e. good management of this resource enables efficient activity. The author who laid the foundations of scientific management, F. Taylor, postulated the principle of *strict time recording and work norming*, taking a huge step towards increasing efficiency in the organization [3]. At present, *management* means the efficient and effective running of an activity. From this perspective, the teacher, as a classroom manager, must know how to manage time resources efficiently in relation to the present needs. Performance-oriented teachers know that time is measurable and continuous, and time management is a priority for the success of an organization. Time, as a key resource, is extremely important not only at an individual level but also at an organizational level. Modern teachers, as a rule, depend directly on the efficiency of their use of time, which has also led to the specification of management on this dimension – time management, which, in current management thinking, is precisely about optimizing the design and planning of teaching activity, focusing on setting objectives, planning, and setting educational priorities. Identifying this dimensionality of time in classroom managerial activity is very important, as it highlights the *notion of rational and efficient use of time* to achieve the desired results [4, p. 286].

Time management is a personal process of planning, anticipating, and reacting in a planned, predictive, effective, and efficient manner (as defined by P. R. Godin), based on three pillars: planning, organizing, and controlling time [1]. The concept of educational/teaching planning may be delimited according to the temporal and spatial resources specifically provided for the achievement of socially and individually determined pedagogical goals. *Organization is a prerequisite for time efficiency*. Well-planned and well-organized activities are enhanced by positive thinking/a positive attitude and communication.

Control is a key pillar in time management. Therefore, the basic paradigm of the third generation is about control based on the principles we establish. This is why institutionalized time management is dependent on the educational curriculum, especially a curriculum that propels the school into the future and is based on the conceptual component, which generalizes between the coordinates of (1) a new educational ideal – the formation of a free, creative, autonomous and open personality, (2) changes in society – the transition to a democratic, computerized society, and (3) new pedagogical trends – the transition to a competence-centered design. On the other hand, this didactic design must aim to place education in the perspec-

tive of (1) lifelong learning, (2) interdisciplinarity and (3) competency-based curriculum as a concept and model for designing and implementing learning [4, p. 290].

Time is a resource that cannot be stored, and how we use it influences our success, health, and happiness. The more organized we are, the less stressed we are, and the better our health will be. At the same time, not managing our time properly puts our health at risk.

Correct time management will contribute to the personal development of teachers, the achievement of their highest goals, personal satisfaction, and fulfillment [10, p. 64]. Of course, for efficient time management, one must take into account *the set priorities, objectives, and plans, how to implement and assess them* etc. Efficient time management is achieved not by solving tasks randomly or in the order they appear, but by relating them to objectives and priorities.

We need to plan very carefully and rigorously:

- which tasks we want to accomplish;
- what is the order of priorities;
- how long it is going to take us to achieve them;
- how our short-term goals relate to our medium- and long-term objectives and planned outcomes;
- resistance to disruptive events and time-wasting tendencies;
- the means by which we monitor the achievement of tasks and how we have planned our work.

Time management is actually self-management. Thus, employing the skills one possesses in order to better plan tasks at work and to delegate responsibilities more effectively is the key to optimal time management [5, p. 186]. Time management/timing has many advantages for teacher managers. It encourages them:

- to achieve the desired goal;
- to set priorities;
- to obtain an overview of the tasks to be accomplished;
- to communicate better;
- to achieve more results per unit of time;
- to delegate tasks;
- to maintain a work-life balance;
- to develop their creativity;
- to overcome difficulties and to better adapt to change;
- to contribute to an improvement in the quality of life of all students in the classroom [5, p. 188].

In this respect, *time control and planning* are crucial. In the field of time management, control consists of measuring the progress or results of tasks carried out, in a given period, in order to identify dysfunctions and correct them. Time control has two purposes: to measure the activities being carried out and to adjust them in line with fluctuations in the variables involved, a psychological purpose linked to the fear that stems

from the term 'control'. We should admit that the need to control time depends on the perception of how each individual uses their time. In general, rigorous time control allows for highlighting:

- the proportion of time allocated/used for each task;
- satisfactory actions within a given time frame;
- problems encountered;
- knowledge acquired;
- results obtained etc.

Time management problems can be solved by implementing timing techniques. The classical time management techniques are: management by objectives, spreadsheets, SWOT analysis, Gantt charts, mind maps, and evaluation of meetings. Much more up-to-date and efficient, but requiring investment, is specific software that allows to adapt the working style to Western standards [5, p. 189].

At academic year level, time management highlights the distribution and sequencing of time devoted to strictly didactic activities, assessment and examination, holidays etc. *The valorization of pedagogical time* implies compliance with the following methodological principles applicable to all the variables involved:

- the distribution of the time reserved for each subject, according to the competences adopted in the school curriculum;
- breaking down the subject matter into teaching units that can be related to time units;
- alternating school activities with predominantly intellectual objectives with activities with mainly moral, technological, aesthetic, and psychophysical objectives, and formal and non-formal training activities;
- the school timetable should be tailored to the pupils' real interests and possibilities, based on the specific circumstances of the school and the subjects studied: faculty council, extracurricular activities, peer lessons etc.

The concept of time management has been imposed as a process of planning and controlling the time used for specific activities, in particular in order to increase its effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity, which may only be achieved through proper organization of educational time – a sequence of social time specialized in preparing persons to enter learning or dedicated to their training in a profession, the formation of socially prescribed behaviors, or the acquisition of specific information. Educational time is the period during which the subjects undergo a training program (directly or indirectly, explicitly or implicitly) at the level of such institutions as family, school, or cultural institutions [9, p. 46].

When referring to time management, we mostly think about professional activity and less about what we do with the rest of our time. But some techniques that are learned for work can also be successfully applied to private life.

There are strategies we can learn in order to manage our time more successfully. Although the idea of time management has been around for more than 100 years, the term *time management* did not come into general use until the 1970s, and it was not until the early 1980s that people began to think of time as a means (resource) that can be managed. Time management is the ability to decide what is important in our lives. A large number of specialists (business and personal coaches) are increasingly promoting and studying the issue of time management as an essential resource in increasing productivity and success in both work and private life. A person with good time management is able to accomplish more tasks in less time, while being more relaxed and able to strike a balance between personal and professional life.

The ability to organize and manage time influences a person's professional success by highlighting their time management pillars: planning, organizing, and controlling time. Identifying time management processes involves:

- defining project activities and determining their sequence, their technological and organizational constraints;
- estimating the duration of the activities, which can be done in a deterministic or probabilistic way;
- the drawing up of the project execution schedule, using classical or modern scheduling methods, depending on complexity;
- monitoring and updating the schedule as it is being fulfilled, which includes measuring and reporting progress in schedule execution and resource use, taking corrective action, and updating and adjusting the schedule [11, p. 277].

There are no “recipes” for time management, but there are methods (prioritization, organization, and planning), techniques (setting targets/objectives); setting organizational/institutional goals; identifying key areas; formulating tasks; setting priorities and tools (SMART model, benchmarking, ABC schemes, diaries, calendars, organizers etc.) for personalizing one's own time management [11, p. 278]. In order to acquire time management skills, teachers must adopt tools and techniques that characterize them and suit their personality, lifestyle and professional activity [11, p. 280].

In conclusion: We should point out that today, when there is a lot of talk of educational reform, the time dimension can be an essential benchmark for achieving quality education, in line with the requirements of the present day, but above all with those of the future and in light of the past. Identifying the dimension of time is highly commendable, as it highlights the notion of efficiency, so as to answer the question of what is being offered to education in the past, the present and the future, and what is the value of this offer. The only thing we can do, in order to turn

time into an ally, is to learn to manage it properly, to learn to set our priorities, to plan carefully the things we have to accomplish and to try and seize opportunities when they arise [6, p. 36].

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